

REFLECTIONS ON THE FORMATION OF REFLEXIVE ABILITIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

Valijon Qodirov

Professor, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences

Andijan State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *The article discusses the concept of reflexive skill, its coverage in pedagogy and psychology. We are also talking about the formation and development of reflexive abilities in preschool children.*

Keywords: *mental abilities, reflexive skill, self-management, assessment, critical attitude, correction, reflexive thinking.*

In our country, much attention is paid to the mental, intellectual, spiritual, moral and physical education of the younger generation, and the necessary conditions have been created for this. It is important to ensure the active participation of children in the educational environment that promotes the formation of reflexive skills among young people, which are factors of mental and spiritual development, pay special attention to the development of creative approach skills based on the organization of cooperation of pupils in the classroom.

In psychology, reflection has the meaning of "the tendency to think about one's own mental state, to fantasize, to think, to analyze one's own state" [8]. As a result of A. Buzman's research in psychology, the phenomenon of reflection has become a special subject of study. He interpreted reflection as the transfer of experiences to the inner world from the outside world and argued that the field of psychology of reflection in psychology should be distinguished [5,32]. In psychology, in the works of Russian scientists such as L.S. Vygotsky, S.L. Rubinstein, A.N. Leontiev, reflection is studied in cognitive, genetic, personal and communicative directions [6].

Scientific work is being carried out on the development of reflexive skills in psychological and pedagogical research of our republic. For example, researcher D. Khakimova describes the concept of reflexive skills of the younger generation as follows:

- Children feel independent and self-governing, speak freely and take an active part;
- analyze your activities, strive for leadership in obtaining new information, and strive for self-development;
- have a high level of motivation to learn;
- recognize the importance and necessity of learning;
- evaluate your activities, develop reflexive thinking [1,34].

Of course, this is not easy in preschool education. Each age group of students requires an individual approach, creative work. In particular, it requires a separate approach in each of the centers of this activity. In this process students' independence is encouraged as much as possible, but it is impossible to achieve success in preschool education without the help of a teacher.

It is necessary to define simplified processes and their stages, which are used as instructions for both the teacher and children. According to psychologist Nargiza Khalilova, when organizing the technology of reflexive education and learning based on communication, the forms of dialogic communication can be as follows: a) understanding of pre-defined goals and learning outcomes; b) comparing tasks necessary for future activities with needs; c) motivation of educational

activities, understanding and assimilation of educational material through logical connections between elements of the educational material and memorization of the content; d) evaluation and correction of the results achieved; e) solving problems by analyzing and summarizing the results of tasks and methods of comparing tasks and requirements; f) self-management, self-control through feedback in educational activities as a result of reflection, development and change of students, their activation as a subject of educational activity[2,18].

Since this recommendation is usually given for all levels of education, we came to the conclusion that it is necessary to adapt specific forms for preschool education. The educator: 1) in accordance with the program and the calendar schedule of work, set tasks to predict the results on the topic under study in the activity centers, evaluate the results to be achieved; 2) planning the motivation mechanism by integrating topics and activity centers; 3) directing the activity of pupils to the goal of making them the subject of learning, to evaluate and adjust in various forms in order to increase their motivation; 4) generalization and summing up of the activities of children; 5) to evaluate their results based on the achievements of pupils, to conduct a critical analysis. Strict observance by the teacher of the principle of creativity (creative approach) during the lesson is a factor in achieving the expected results. It is important to provide students with a system of leading questions and tasks that will allow them to self-control, analyze and evaluate your activities consciously, creatively and independently.

They can be something like this: 1. why should I do this? (Why should I paint this picture in this color? Or why should I memorize this poem? 2. What will (or) let me do (or know) this? 3. I need to find out what are the similarities and differences from those who studied (tried, remembered, etc.). 4. What did I learn from this? How did I understand my achievements and shortcomings? Through this activity in in a sense, problem-based learning begins, and in the system of problem - based learning, the method of developing reflexive competencies proposed by O.S. Anisimov approaches practice [4].

Any knowledge, skills and experience related to the independent activity of children are formed primarily in the classroom. Even the beginning of the habit of independent learning and the process of becoming a lifestyle are directly related to activities in activity centers. A child who is not interested in studying the material, who, participating in the analysis, has not tasted the pleasure of revealing the hidden meaning of the text, does not want to think independently, and as a result it is impossible to involve him in this type of activity.

Independent thinking and knowledge cannot be introduced forcibly; in this case it will become not independent, but forced education. If a child enjoys independent work through classes in activity centers and is satisfied with it, there is a spiritual need for learning and activity. To satisfy this need, he voluntarily engages in other activities. It follows from this that reflexive skills are first formed in the activity of activity centers, and then gradually transferred to the process of self-study and execution. Dialogues occupy a special place in the formation of such skills [3].

The center of the dialogues is mainly the communication between the educator and the child, questions and tasks that are performed with the help of these questions or separately from them. Questions and tasks are necessary for the educator so that he can guide the students to the goal. Given the age of the child, the questions may vary slightly – be simplified or complex [7,63]. For example, in small age groups, giving pictures for coloring, the teacher asks: "In what color will you paint an apple?" "Is it possible to paint an apple in blue, except red?", "Is it possible to paint an apple in yellow?", "Is it possible to paint an apple in black?" Another way is to put an

image of an apple in front of them and ask them to choose colored pencils for coloring, and ask why these pencils were chosen?, such questions will give children a line of reflexive abilities. At the lessons of acquaintance with nature, on the one hand, pets: sheep, cow, dog, cat, goat; on the other for example, wild animals: wolf, fox, lion, are mixed and given a practical task to show which of them can be brought together, and children divide them into groups.

When the task is completed, each child explains his task. Explaining why he did it or not will give him an opportunity to evaluate the results of his work.

In middle-aged children, this question and the task should be slightly complicated. When they read a fairy tale, they ask to retell it. Positive and negative images in fairy tales can be considered a convenient tool of the educator in the formation of reflexive abilities. For example, in the fairy tale "Zumrad and Kimmat" children are asked to evaluate each of the two characters of the fairy tale. When they give their estimates, they should explain why they give such estimates. It would be appropriate for the educator to ask them what they would do in their place.

In the older age group, when this fairy tale is repeated, tasks and questions should serve to deepen reflexive abilities. For example, "What would you do if you were in Zumrad's place?", "How would you correct your mistakes if you were in Kimmat's place?" It is also a good idea to give tasks such as "Imagine if you are in a fairy tale, what you would say to Zumrad" or "Tell me one by one, what would you like to say to Kimmat?"

In the centers of design, manufacture and mathematical images, it may be appropriate for children to ask questions about their attitude and assessments of the model after, how they created and prepared a model, device, or other form of model.

A child, who sees his strengths and weaknesses, reflexively refers to personal activities. At the same time, it is useful to hear the opinion of other children in the group about his actions (speech, conclusion, etc.). This can be done based on the age group of children, their drawings, which they draw, the songs they sing, the things they do, the fairy tales they listen to, the conclusions they draw from legends. It teaches children to look at their work from the point of view of others. The advantage of collective analysis is that by listening to each other's conclusions, participants learn a lot.

If this method has been used consistently, if it is used in each activity center with appropriate methods and tools, the formation of reflexive skills will occur in front of the educator. At the same time a pupil who is able to evaluate his own and others' activities tends to move independently, speak freely and be active; strives to play a leading role in the analysis of educational activities and obtaining new information; the most important thing is a high level of preparation and motivation, the ability to self-esteem, adjustment.

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